

Linux Foundation Seminars and sessions Notes

By: Samer Attrah

Fundamentals of Embedded Linux - Chris Simmons - NDC TechTown 2022 on youtube:

- Embedded systems have no formal definition, but it could be described as code running on a computer inside a device that you do not think of as a computer.
- Smart phones are kind of the boundary between the embedded and non-embedded.
- Embedded systems have three categories:
 - o Microcontroller (MCU): such as washing machine.
 - o Microprocessor (MPU): mostly x86 architecture.
 - o System on chip (SoC): MPU with on chip peripherals, mostly ARM architecture.
- Categories of embedded linux hardware:
 - o SBC: single board computers like raspberry pi
 - o SoM: system-on-module which is an SoC plus supporting circuitry
 - o Custom hardware: board designed for a specific purpose
- MCUs that are so small runs code bare metal, while mid and high end uses a real time operating system (RTOS) such as Zephyr, NuttX, FreeRTOS.
- Embedded MPU and SoC predominantly uses embedded linux.
- Some negative part when using embedded linux is that it may lack support for a particular hardware, updates may not be delivered as rapid as possible, SoC, SoM, SBC does not always push fixes as quickly as we would like.
- When using linux there are two choices:
 - o Using distros such as debian or ubuntu, and this one is not the best idea because it means native compilation and that is whenever you want to compile a program you must do it on the embedded system, and distros are usually too big.
 - o Build from source: which is the best choice because it enables cross compilation which means you can compile any program away from the embedded system and then run it on the system.
- Boards needs a board support packages (BSP) which include everything you need to run linux on a particular board.

- Every embedded linux project has these elements:

- o Toolchain: to compile all the other elements.
 - o Bootloader: to initialize the board and run the kernel.
 - o Kernel: to manage system resources.
 - o Root filesystem: to run applications.
- Raspberry pi is not the best out there because it runs an operating system from a SD card which is not a good idea, and for that reason using system-on-module is recommended

LF live mentorship session: a whistlestop tour of embedded linux:

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